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A scheduling optimization model of electric water heaters for electricity cost minimization with limited information

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Abstract—The present paper defines the equations that govern the optimization model of an electric water heater in order to manage automatically its available flexibility for the user's own benefit. A case study that focuses on the electric water heater flexibility potential is carried out: it is aimed to minimize the total expected electricity cost of a single household that only has an electric water heater as a flexibility source. The temperature inside the hot water tank is an unknown value since the temperature sensor is not sending any information outside. Moreover, real hot water consumption is uncertain and the model takes decisions based on forecasting models. Given the limited information available, the model is developed in a conservative way with the objective of maintaining both, the hot water temperature and the user's comfort. The results show that it is possible to reduce the electricity bill by managing optimally the available flexibility from the electric water heater.

Index Terms—Electricity markets; Smart Grid; Flexibility; Optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Europe is making efforts to fight the climate change by adopting an ambitious renewable energy policy [1] that sets a target of at least 32% of renewable share on average in the European countries by 2030. By imposing these carbon free energy policies and acting at European Union (EU) level, economies of scale can be achieved, which will contribute to a continuous and faster technology development and settlement.

As a direct consequence of promoting and encouraging the renewable energy production, intermittent and variable power generation will be greater, which results in a bigger need for flexibility in the electrical system. [2] defines flexibility as the modification of generation injection and/or consumption patterns in reaction to an external signal (price signal or activation) in order to provide a service within the energy system [2]. Due to these unpredictable and intermittent sources of power generation, companies from the electricity sector have now a greater difficulty in guaranteeing the quality of the electricity supply. Due to this energy market context, the aggregator figure has emerged and it is playing an important

role in optimizing electricity generation and demand of its portfolio and helping the stability of the grid by providing the needed flexibility. As instance, there are certain time periods throughout the year where the electricity demand is really high, so instead of building new power plants, it makes more sense to cut out that peak by using the user's available flexibility, which will result in lower costs and greater efficiency for the electrical system.

According to the Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [3], there are three main flexibility sources that could provide flexibility:

- Demand Response (DR): its purpose is to influence the electricity demand in response to financial incentives for shifting or curtailing their electricity consumption. DR can reduce consumer bills, lower carbon emissions and make more efficient use of our existing electricity generators.
- Energy Storage Systems: self-consumption can be improved by storing the surplus of intermittent renewable generation for later use when needed.
- Distributed Generation: flexibility provided by renewable energy production of local generation units. Electricity production can be curtailed or reduced to match local demand in order to keep the grid balanced.

The present study will only focus on the DR flexibility source. Up until now, the electricity industry has only provided flexibility to the grid on the generation side by changing the amount of energy injected into the grid in order to match the demand. Now the end-users can participate also in the flexibility market through the DR program, thanks to recent developments in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) that have allowed the Smart Grid to have a bidirectional communication system between the utility and the end-user. The Smart Grid concept is also about giving the customers the information and tools they need so they can make intelligent choices about how to manage their renewable

generation and electricity consumption at home in an optimal way. Such decisions as rescheduling the consumption of an electrical appliance are made by Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS) [4], a technology platform comprised of both hardware and software that enables the residential customers to execute DR programs autonomously. The HEMS also allows to monitor the energy usage and production thanks to smart sensors and meters installed in each household. The HEMS could be executed locally or via cloud computing through a communication network, which is usually the Internet. Thus, the HEMS via cloud computing can manage the electrical devices without having to setup and maintain a local network, thereby improving the efficiency, flexibility and cost savings [5].

A. Electric Water Heaters Literature Review

Thanks to the intelligent DR management and to the bidirectional system of information and energy, residential aggregated Electric Water Heaters (EWHs) loads can actively participate in peak and frequency regulations, increasing the energy efficiency, robustness and security of the electricity grid. In return, end-users will be rewarded financially for activating flexibility. They can also sign up to hourly changing electricity tariffs and the HEMS will assign an optimal consumption schedule for each residential EWH, with the aim of reducing the electricity bill, ensuring that the user's comfort is not greatly diminished.

These two different EWH flexibility services mentioned above are divided and defined by Olivella-Rosell [6] under the framework of local flexibility markets:

- Distribution System Operator (DSO)-centered flexibility service: clustering EWHs as a flexible resource has several benefits for the electricity distributors. Aggregated residential EWHs can help in congestion management by reducing peak loads periods and providing balancing and regulation services. The DSO sends a flexibility request to the aggregator, who manages all the EWH available flexibility in its portfolio in order to give that flexibility claimed.
- End-user-centered flexibility service: aims to minimize/reduce the household's energy bill in response to dynamic electricity price signals, thanks to relocating flexible home appliances consumption from peak-hours to cheaper periods.

Many studies have focused on models that aggregate residential EWHs [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] as a flexibility service system in order to provide a service to the grid such as peak shaving or frequency control. By using a centralized control of a large number of EWHs, users can offer bidding strategies through the aggregator to get more revenues.

A voltage-control strategy for power management of aggregated residential EWHs is proposed by Nehrir [7]. This method is mainly a flexibility service for the DSO: the total power demand of residential EWH loads during peak-load hours can be controlled.

A detailed thermal stratification model inside the water tank along with a statistical model for populations of EWHs is described by Vrettos [8]. Four control approaches are presented for aggregating power set point tracking, using as a scaled load frequency control as a control signal.

Moradzadeh [9] proposes an algorithm to control the thermostat set point of a group of EWHs within the distribution system with the aim of mitigating the peak demand of the increasing electric vehicles while meeting the hot water demand requirements. Results show how the peak demand is flattened.

An accurate partial differential equation physics-based model that captures the detailed temperature profile has been developed by Xu [10]. This model can be used as a good benchmark to simulate a large number of residential EWHs for DR control.

Literature also focus on single EWH optimization [12], [13], [14], [15], where the hot water temperature inside the tank is a known parameter in all the references mentioned.

In order to establish an optimal EWH scheduling model, two EWH load shifting strategies were proposed by Wu [12]: advanced and delayed heating strategy according to the direct load control method. EWH is considered a transferable load, relocating its energy consumption from the peak to the flat and valley hours. End-user comfort is always considered as the highest priority.

Ahmed [13] studies the DR possibilities of a residential EWH, the overall consumption and temperature profile and the end-user economic benefit. Real-time electricity pricing with incentive-based DR is considered. The study compares the results between normal consumption and consumption after using a direct load control. Water temperature, ambient temperature, water usage and physical characteristics are considered as the EWH parameters. In this case, a single EWH for every residential household is considered.

A heuristic algorithm is presented by Kapsalis [14] for the purpose of scheduling the operation of a single EWH under dynamic electricity pricing, which minimizes the energy cost without compromising the comfort level. The EWH can operate either in a cost or comfort-oriented mode.

Wang [15] presents a single EWH user's optimal bidding strategy and analyzes the relationship between profit, market clearing price and bidding strategy coefficients.

The novelty of this work is the development of an EWH model that is able to reschedule its electricity consumption optimally, having no water tank temperature information and with an uncertainty in the EWH forecast consumption. For this reason, it has been decided to be conservative in the use of flexibility, prioritizing first the comfort of the end-user.

B. Outline of the Paper

The present work is organized as follows: Section II describes the EWH model. The EWH mathematical formulation, the objective function and Spanish electricity market constraints implemented in the EWH scheduling model optimization are presented in Section III. The case study definition is

presented in Section IV and its results are shown and explained in Section V. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section VI.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The present study is focused on the end-user-centered flexibility service for controlling a domestic EWH. The objective function will minimize/reduce the end-user electricity bill in response to hourly changes in electricity prices, thanks to relocating the EWH flexible consumption from expensive to cheaper periods.

The EWH model proposed has no temperature value from inside the hot water storage tank, since the temperature sensor is not sending this information to the HEMS platform. The consumption can only be postpone, it can never be shifted to previous time intervals.

The domestic EWH model consists mainly in a shiftable energy volume load model that is able to disconnect the EWH when needed and it considers the re-bounce effect. Hence, if there is a load curtailment, it will always supply the exactly same amount of curtailed energy afterwards within the corresponding shifting interval.

The main contribution of this work has to do with including specific timing restrictions in the model: maximum disconnection duration ($D_l^{ewh,max}$), minimum time between two disconnections ($D_l^{ewh,min}$) and time intervals where it is not allowed to disconnect the EWH ($C_l^{ewh,allow}$). The end-user imposes these parameters values depending on how much he is willing to reduce his comfort.

All of them are explained below:

- $C_l^{ewh,allow}$: There could be inflexible intervals, where the EWH baseline consumption cannot be shifted/controlled. For each period, a parameter says whether it is allowed to disconnect the water heater or not (e.g. disconnection is allowed at any time, except from between 19:00h and 22:00h).
- $D_l^{ewh,max}$: A maximum disconnection duration is given (e.g. if the water heater is disconnected, it must be reconnected after 1:30 hour) This parameter indicates the maximum number of time periods available for disconnection during each load shift interval. The number of disconnections do not have to be consecutive.
- $D_l^{ewh,min}$: A minimum duration (rest time) between two disconnections is given (e.g. if a water heater is reconnected after a disconnection, it cannot be disconnected again before at least 3 hours). This parameter ensures the minimum duration between successive activations: a minimum number of consecutive time periods is established in which the EWH cannot be disconnected under any circumstances. This restriction is imposed due to uncertainty, since the water temperature inside the EWH is not available. This parameter enables the EWH to recover the temperature inside the water tank.

A simple case study is proposed for the sole purpose of facilitating the explanation, making it easier to check and understand how the EWH scheduling optimization model behaves and shifts depending on the hourly price and restrictions.

III. ELECTRIC WATER HEATER MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

In this section the mathematical formulation will be introduced.

A. Objective Function

The end-user can only purchase energy from the grid, because the household has neither a renewable generator or an energy storage system. The objective is to minimize the electricity bill of each household individually without incurring in a high discomfort for the end-user. The objective function formulated in equation 1 has into account the total cost of buying electricity from the grid and the discomfort cost (ζ^{ewh}) for activating the EWH flexibility.

$$\min_{\chi_t^{buy}, \zeta^{ewh}} = \sum_{t \in T} (P_t^{retail,buy} \cdot \chi_t^{buy} \cdot P^{taxes}) + \zeta^{ewh} \quad (1)$$

The discomfort term refers to the minimum savings in the electricity bill needed for activating flexibility.

B. Automatic Generation of Flexibility Sessions for the EWH

Once the beginning and the end of each EWH baseline interval consumption are found ($T_{l,i}^{start}$ and $V_{l,i}^{end}$), the end of each shifting interval ($T_{l,i}^{end}$) is imposed by the following restriction:

$$T_{l,i}^{end} = V_{l,i}^{end} + D_l^{ewh,max} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I \quad (2)$$

The shifting interval i is understood as the set of time-periods in which the flexibility is allowed to be activated.

Once all the parameters mentioned above are establish, we make sure to meet the following two restrictions. If they do not meet, the $T_{l,i}^{end}$ assigned value in eq. 2 must be changed and moved to previous positions, thus reducing the available flexibility time intervals.

Restriction 1: there is at least $D_l^{ewh,min}$ time intervals where the EWH can not be controlled or shifted. We set this restriction in order to reestablish the nominal temperature inside the hot water tank if needed. During these time intervals, an ON signal is sent to the EWH, so if the water temperature is below the minimum, the EWH will start to heat.

There must be at least $D_l^{ewh,min}$ periods before the next shifting interval begins:

$$T_{l,i+1}^{start} - T_{l,i}^{end} \geq D_l^{ewh,min} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I \quad (3)$$

If Restriction 1 (eq. 3) does not meet, $T_{l,i}^{start} - T_{l,i}^{end}$ value could be either positive or negative:

- Positive value: $0 \leq T_{l,i+1}^{start} - T_{l,i}^{end} < D_l^{ewh,min}$

Solution proposed: Move $T_{l,i}^{end}$ backwards.

The parameter $T_{l,i+1}^{start}$ maintains the same time interval position, while $T_{l,i}^{end}$ is brought backwards in order to meet the $D_l^{ewh,min}$ restriction. As a result, the previous

shift interval have less time periods available for flexibility, because $[T_{l,i}^{start}, T_{l,i}^{end}]$ is shortened. The new $T_{l,i}^{end}$ value would be:

$$T_{l,i}^{end} = T_{l,i}^{start} - D_l^{ewh,min} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I \quad (4)$$

It does not make sense that $T_{l,i}^{end} < V_{l,i}^{end}$, so if this happens, we equal values $T_{l,i}^{end} = V_{l,i}^{end}$, becoming that shift interval i in a non-flexible one. In Figure 1, the shifting interval $i=1$ is inflexible due to this.

- Negative value: $T_{l,i+1}^{start} - T_{l,i}^{end} < 0$
Solution proposed: Move $T_{l,i}^{end}$ backwards.

$$T_{l,i}^{end} = T_{l,i}^{end} - |T_{l,i+1}^{start} - T_{l,i}^{end}| - D_l^{ewh,min} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I \quad (5)$$

Like it has been explained before, if $T_{l,i}^{end} < V_{l,i}^{end}$, values are equal $T_{l,i}^{end} = V_{l,i}^{end}$.

Restriction 2: ensures that there is, at most, $D_l^{ewh,max}$ time periods where the baseline consumption can be shifted/controlled in each shifting interval $i \in I$.

$$V_{l,i}^{end} \leq T_{l,i}^{end} \leq V_{l,i}^{end} + D_l^{ewh,max} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I \quad (6)$$

It also has to be ensured that there is no $W_{l,t}^{ewh,restrict}$ consumption shifted to periods when $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = 0$. So during the periods where $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = 0$, it is not allowed to control/curtail the EWH consumption. Due to this, we cannot shift the EWH consumption to periods where $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = 0$. Because of this, there must be set an inflexible shift interval.

So, if $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = 0$ and during the time interval before there is a consumption and the present time interval does too, then: $T_{l,i}^{end} = V_{l,i}^{end}$.

Figure 1 summarizes what it has been explained in this section and how the flexibility sessions or shifting intervals are set $D_l^{ewh,max} = 3$ and $D_l^{ewh,min} = 1$:

Fig. 1. Graphic explanation of $D_l^{ewh,min}$, $D_l^{ewh,max}$ and the shifting intervals I.

C. EWH Rescheduling Model Formulation

For each time interval, the parameter $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow}$ says whether it is allowed to disconnect the EWH or not:

$$W_{l,t}^{ewh,restrict} = W_{l,t}^{ewh} \cdot C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} \quad \forall l \in L, t \in T \quad (7)$$

The total amount of energy consumption in each time period can be controlled between a minimum $Q_l^{ewh,min}/N$ and a maximum $Q_l^{ewh,max}/N$ value. In this EWH particular case, we want an ON/OFF control type, so the EWH will be turned on the time intervals needed to meet the final amount of energy consumed $\omega_{l,t}^{ewh,realconsum}$.

For each shift interval i , the sum of the energy volume delivered to the load unit must equal the sum of the baseline forecast:

$$\sum_{t=T_{l,i}^{start}}^{T_{l,i}^{end}} \omega_{l,t}^{ewh} = \sum_{t=T_{l,i}^{start}}^{T_{l,i}^{end}} W_{l,t}^{ewh,restrict} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I, t \in T \quad (8)$$

There could be inflexible intervals (for example, during periods where there is an EWH baseline consumption and $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = 0$), where the EWH baseline consumption cannot be shifted/controlled. $W_{l,t}^{ewh,allow}$ is a parameter that indicates the baseline consumption when $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = 0$. The energy delivered to the EWH unit must equal the baseline forecast during the periods where there is no shifting interval i .

$$W_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = W_{l,t}^{ewh} \quad \forall l \in L, t \notin T(i) \quad (9)$$

In order to know the final and real EWH consumption, the parameter $W_{l,t}^{ewh,allow}$ must be added to the optimized $\omega_{l,t}^{ewh}$.

$$\omega_{l,t}^{ewh,realconsum} = W_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} + \omega_{l,t}^{ewh} \quad \forall l \in L, t \in T \quad (10)$$

The concept of weighted average delay is introduced:

$$\tau_{l,i}^{ewh} = \frac{\sum_{t=T_{l,i}^{start}}^{T_{l,i}^{end}} ((\omega_{l,t}^{ewh} - W_{l,t}^{ewh,restrict}) \cdot t)}{\sum_{t=T_{l,i}^{start}}^{T_{l,i}^{end}} W_{l,t}^{ewh,restrict}} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I \quad (11)$$

The total cost for shifting the EWH consumption is:

$$\zeta_{l,i}^{ewh} = P_l^{ewh,shift} \cdot \tau_{l,i}^{ewh} \quad \forall l \in L, i \in I \quad (12)$$

D. Inflexible Load

Inflexible loads relate to appliances that can not be controlled, which implies that they can not be shifted to later hours or curtailed, therefore, these appliances do not participate in DR. They run without any delay and with the highest priority.

$$\omega_{l,t}^{inflex} = W_{l,t}^{inflex} \quad \forall l \in L, t \in T \quad (13)$$

E. Market Tariff Constraints

The total electricity imported from the grid χ_t^{buy} must be equal to the consumption of flexible loads (EWH) and inflexible loads, for each time period $t \in T$:

$$\chi_t^{buy} = \sum_{l \in L} \omega_{l,t}^{ewh,realconsum} + \sum_{l \in L^i} W_{l,t}^{inflex} \quad \forall t \in T \quad (14)$$

The electricity imported must be less or equal to the contracted power of each end-user, according to the terms stipulated in the retail contract. In the present study the value is set to 10 kW.

$$\chi_t^{buy} \leq X^{max,imp} / N \quad \forall t \in T \quad (15)$$

IV. CASE STUDY

This study belongs to the customer-centered flexibility service category. It is aimed to control and reschedule optimally the EWH consumption with the main objective of reducing the electricity bill of a household with a Spanish PVPC tariff (Precio Voluntario para el Pequeño Consumidor) with hourly discrimination [16]. The fact that the electricity price changes hourly allows to see how the EWH baseline consumption shifts from expensive to cheaper time intervals. The study considers the Spanish retail electricity market, in which the end-users with the PVPC tariff have a contracted power less or equal to 10 kW. As it has been already pointed out, the household will not have any renewable generation, such as photovoltaic panels, neither energy storage system, being the EWH the only flexible source available in the house.

In order to make the case study as realistic as possible, real household electricity consumption data provided by Pecan Street Inc. Dataport 2018 database [17] has been used: real inflexible load and domestic EWH consumption are an input parameter in the EWH scheduling model.

The planing horizon is one entire day and each time interval is 15 minutes long, making a total of 96 periods. The optimization horizon starts at 00:00h.

It is expected that the consumption of EWH will shift towards periods where electricity is cheaper, always complying with the restrictions imposed in section III.

Some input parameters are shown in Figure 2: The domestic EWH forecast consumption, the total inflexible load, the purchase price of electricity without taxes and the base net load, which is the total amount of energy purchased to the grid in the baseline case (before running the EWH scheduling optimization). The price for activating flexibility has been set in 0.01€/kWh. $D_l^{ewh,min}$ is 1 period and $D_l^{ewh,max}$ is 12 periods.

V. RESULTS

The EWH rescheduling optimization model results are displayed in Figure 3. By looking at the hourly electricity purchase price curve, it can be seen how the EWH consumption is postponed over time when the electricity price in the following time intervals belonging to each shift interval is cheaper than

Fig. 2. Input parameters of the EWH model. Source: Pecan Street Inc. Dataport 2018

the baseline consumption. The net energy exchange curve is the final amount of energy purchased to the grid after the EWH rescheduling. Comparing this curve with the base net load, it is observed that during the most expensive electricity prices periods, the electricity purchased to the grid decreases (e.g. time intervals 2, 85 and 90), increasing during cheaper periods (e.g. time intervals 4, 60 and 92).

Fig. 3. EWH rescheduling model optimization results. Source: Pecan Street Inc. Dataport 2018

The output of the present EWH model is a set of disconnection and re-connection periods. The control signals will be off and on with a given time, 15 minutes in this case. By relocating the EWH consumption, savings of 6.80% in the EWH electricity costs have been achieved: the cost decreased from 33.69 c€ to 31.39 c€.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Despite having no access to data from the EWH thermostat, the cost of the energy consumed by the EWH was reduce around a 7% by rescheduling the EWH baseline consumption in an optimal way, from expensive peak-hours to cheaper time intervals. This model is conservative in terms of available flexibility to make sure that the user's comfort is not diminished, so there is not long periods where the EWH is curtailed, thanks to the timing restrictions. As a future work, it would be interesting to study the EWH aggregation in order to offer flexibility services to the DSO.

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APPENDIX

A. Sets

I	Set of load shift intervals of EWH
L	Subset of load units that are EWH
L^i	Subset of load units that are inflexible
T	Set of periods in the planning horizon

B. Parameters

$C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow}$	Binary parameter equal to 1 if disconnection of EWH unit $l \in L$ is allowed in period $t \in T$, else 0. [-]
$D_l^{ewh,max}$	Maximum duration of flexibility activation of the EWH unit $l \in L$ [ptu]
$D_l^{ewh,min}$	Minimum rest time between two successive shifting intervals $i \in I$ of the EWH unit $l \in L$ in time periods [ptu]
$Q_l^{ewh,max}$	Maximum power level of EWH unit $l \in L$ [kW]
$Q_l^{ewh,min}$	Minimum power level of EWH unit $l \in L$ [kW]
N	Number of time intervals per hour [-]
$P_t^{ewh,shift}$	Price for shifting EWH demand volume for the unit $l \in L$ [€]
$P_t^{retail,buy}$	Price for purchasing electricity from the grid in period $t \in T$ [€/kWh]
P^{taxes}	Electricity bill VAT tax. Constant parameter [-]
$T_{l,i}^{start}$	First period for EWH unit $l \in L$ in shift interval $i \in I$ [ptu]
$T_{l,i}^{end}$	Last period for EWH unit $l \in L$ in shift interval $i \in I$ [ptu]
$V_{l,i}^{end}$	Last period in EWH shift interval $i \in I$ where the EWH unit $l \in L$ has a baseline consumption [ptu]
$W_{l,t}^{ewh}$	Baseline consumption of of EWH unit $l \in L$ in period $t \in T$ [kWh]
$W_{l,t}^{ewh,allow}$	Baseline consumption of EWH unit $l \in L$ when $C_{l,t}^{ewh,allow} = 0$ in time period $t \notin (T_{l,i}^{start}, T_{l,i}^{end})$ [kWh]
$W_{l,t}^{ewh,restrict}$	Restricted baseline consumption of EWH unit $l \in L$ in time period $t \in [T_{l,i}^{start}, T_{l,i}^{end}]$ [kWh]
$W_{l,t}^{inflex}$	Inflexible load consumption of load unit $l \in L^i$ in time period $t \in T$ [kWh]
$X^{max,imp}$	Contracted power. Maximum power allowed by contract to import from the grid [kW]

C. Variables

$\tau_{l,i}^{ewh}$	Weighted average delay of EWH unit $l \in L$ in shift interval $i \in I$ in number of time periods [p.u.]
$\omega_{l,t}^{ewh}$	Amount of electricity consumed from EWH unit $l \in L$ in time period $t \in [T_{l,i}^{start}, T_{l,i}^{end}]$ [kWh]
$\omega_{l,t}^{ewh,realconsum}$	Real amount of electricity consumed from EWH unit $l \in L$ in time period $t \in T$ [kWh]
χ_t^{buy}	Amount of electricity bought in period $t \in T$ [kWh]
$\zeta_{l,i}^{ewh}$	Total cost for shifting the demand volume of the EWH unit $l \in L$ in shift interval $i \in I$ [€]

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